

Airborne and Ground Induced Polarization integration: new insights for exploration

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SUMMARY

It is known and recognized that Induced Polarization effects can affect the Airborne Electromagnetic measurements. These effects, if not treated properly, can represent a source of artifacts, bad fitting, and false recovered structures during the inversion process. At the same time, recognize and properly model the polarization effects can provide a mapping of the spectral content of the recorded data, adding extra information to the results, and allows to properly model the EM. With this work, we modelled the spectral content of Airborne EM data and compared the results with ground IP measurements acquired in the same area. For the modelling procedure, we propose to use the same approach, in order to be more consistent in the modelling procedure. The data we used are from the Iberian Pyrite Belt, one of the most important mining districts in Europe and with the highest concentration of VMS worldwide. Given the geological complexity of the area and the different signatures of the mineralisation style, with our data integration we aim to evaluate the potentialities of the AIP modelling and its role for exploration.

Key words: Airborne Electromagnetics, Induced Polarization, Mineral Exploration.

INTRODUCTION

The Iberian Pyrite Belt (IPB) is one of the oldest and still active mining districts in the world. In the last decade, a renewed mining activity and scientific research have led into a wealth of new data and new geological hints for explorers and for the academic community, making the IPB one of the most important and dynamic mining districts in Europe (Inverno et al, 2015). The reason for the great interest in the IPB (*figure 1*), which forms part of the Hercynian orogenic belt, is that its Late Devonian to Middle Carboniferous rocks host a huge quantity of volcanic-hosted massive sulphide (VMS) mineralization (1700 Mt of sulphides, totalling 14.6 Mt Cu, 13.0 Mt Pb, 34.9 Mt Zn, 46100 t Ag and 880 t Au), that make the region as the one with the highest concentration of sulphides worldwide (Leistel et al, 1998).

Figure 1. Overview of the major deposits in the Iberian Pirite Belt and location of the Escacena survey area (image from PanGlobal)

The mineralization and its environment display a number of different signatures that are related to the mineralogy and zoning of the sulphide orebodies, calling for the integrated use of complementary geophysical methods. The sulfides targets show contrast in both density and electrical properties, and historically gravity has played a crucial role for exploring in the IPB. These methods have been later accompanied by EM methodologies (both airborne and ground), given their high sensitivity to conductive targets (Menghini et al, 2022). Regarding the EM methods, it is known and accepted how these are sensitive to Induced Polarization effects (AIP) when acquired over a polarizable halfspace (Kratzer and Macnae, 2012; Viezzoli et al., 2013). Modelling the capacitive effects present in the AEM data allow to parametrize and map the spectral content of the polarizable materials, that are widely spread in the shallow subsurface and that often present significant economic value (or signatures of the mineralization). Physically, the polarization processes cause currents in the opposite direction of the eddy currents due to conduction, determining a distortion of the recorded electromagnetic signal, which often culminate in its change of sign at late times in presence of strong chargeable anomalies. Under these conditions, the standard EM inversion approaches, which does not account for polarization currents, ceases to be valid (Smith and Klein, 1996): negative data cannot be fitted and fast-decaying signals caused by polarization are misinterpreted as due to strong resistors. It follows that modelling the AIP effects is crucial to recover realistic electric properties and geometries of the investigated areas and to properly fit the data, in presence of polarizable rocks.

With this contribution we will show an application of airborne IP modelling for mineral exploration in the Pyritic Belt and a comparison of the AIP models with the modelling of several ground IP lines, acquired in the same area. The comparison aims to better understand the potential of the use of AIP for exploration and to attempt an improvement in the definition of the sensitivity field of the airborne technique, as well as its relationships with ground IP. Among the differences between the two methodologies, the most obvious ones are differences in footprint, depth of investigation, spectral content, with AEM data's frequency bandwidth usually a couple of orders of magnitudes higher than that of ground IP data. The latter point suggests that ground and airborne IP may excite different chargeable particles. Beside these problems, another major issue, not always recognized, is the difference in the modelling approach. Ground IP data is usually modelled dropping the spectral information, e.g., turning a full secondary voltage decay into a single value of integral chargeability (e.g. Oldenburg and Li, 1994). Moreover, the effect of current waveform is often not modelled, resulting in inversion models in which the retrieved polarization magnitude strongly depends on the acquisition settings of the current waveform, making a quantitative comparison between AIP and Ground IP impossible (Olsson et al., 2019). On the contrary, in this study we model the IP spectral content in both AIP and Ground IP data, in terms of the Maximum Phase Angle (MPA) re-parameterization of the Cole-Cole model (Fiandaca et al., 2018), and the current waveform is fully taken into account both in AIP data and Ground IP data, which are inverted as full transients (Fiandaca et al., 2012; Fiandaca et al., 2013). Using the same modelling approach allows for a quantitative comparison of ground IP and AIP results for better interpretation, and, ultimately, for a quantitative integration of the modelling of the 2 datasets, i.e. for joint inversion. This paper shows the potential benefits of such approach on a dataset comprising AIP data and ground IP data acquired for the Escacena project, an exploration project of PanGlobal Inc, a Canadian mining company which is exploring in the IPB.

SURVEY AREA AND GEOLOGY

The Escacena Project is located in Andalusia, in southern Spain, close to the known Aznacollar VMS deposit, as shown in figure 1. The tenement's area is developed around several gravimetric anomalies, of which the most explored and significant is the "La Romanera" deposit, i.e., a shallow Volcanic Massive copper Sulphide, firstly located with a gravimetric anomaly and then shown by EM methods and ground IP. For this deposit, the geophysical anomalies have been confirmed by drillings showing a significative tenure of copper and strontium.

Geologically, the typical IPB sequence is given by a lowermost stratigraphic unit constituted by the early Givetian to late Famennian-Strunian Phyllite-Quartzite Group (PQG), with shales, quartz-sandstones and quartzwacke siltstones. The PQG is overlain by the Volcanic Sedimentary Complex (VSC), of late Famennian to mid-late Viséan age, with a lower part of mafic volcanic rocks, rhyolites, dacites and dark shales, hosting VHMS deposits on top (many times capped by a jasper/chert layer), and an upper part, with dark shales and volcanogenic/volcaniclastic rocks, carrying Mn oxide deposits (Inverno,2016).

The geology of the survey area is shown in figure 2: a large sedimentary cover given by silty conglomerates is present in the south, which passes to the outcropping volcanic rock of the VSC domain in the north with a medium belt of slates and limestones.

Figure 2. Geology of the Escacena exploration area.

GEOPHYSICAL METHODS AND RESULTS

The Airborne EM data have been acquired the last spring with the NRG XCite Time Domain system (with 25Hz base frequency), and the acquisition lines are illustrated in black lines in figure 3. In the same area, 18 SyscalPro lines (0.125Hz of base frequency, 50% duty cycle) of ground Time Domain DCIP have been acquired (red lines in figure 3).

Figure 3. Survey location. In black the Airborne EM lines are displayed, in red the DCIP.

Both EM and galvanic IP datasets have been modelled in terms of the MPA re-parameterization (Fiandaca et al., 2018) of the Cole-Cole model, following Fiandaca et al. (2013) for galvanic data and Fiandaca et Viezzoli (2021) for inductive data. In particular, the galvanic data have been modelled in 2D in terms of full-voltage decay (instead of the integral chargeability), taking into account the transmitter waveform and the receiver transfer function, for quantitative estimation of the spectral parameters. The inductive data have been modelled in 1D, and in order to reduce the parametric equivalences and to enhance the modelling resolution in AIP modelling, the C and Time Constants' parameters vary only horizontally in the model space, while resistivity and maximum phase change also with depth. In the MPA Cole-Cole model the maximum phase φ_{max} of the complex conductivity and the phase relaxation time $\tau\varphi$ are used instead of $m0$ and $\tau\rho$. The phase of the complex conductivity can be defined in terms of both equations 1 and 2 as:

$$\varphi(\omega) = tg^{-1} \left(\frac{\sigma''(\omega)}{\sigma'(\omega)} \right) = -tg^{-1} \left(\frac{\rho''(\omega)}{\rho'(\omega)} \right) \quad (\text{eq.1})$$

The phase reaches his maximum φ_{max} at an angular frequency $\omega_{\varphi=1/\tau\varphi}$ as:

$$\varphi_{max} = tg^{-1} \left(\frac{\sigma''(1/\tau\varphi)}{\sigma'(1/\tau\varphi)} \right) = tg^{-1} \left(\frac{\rho''(1/\tau\varphi)}{\rho'(1/\tau\varphi)} \right) \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

Furthermore, the model space of the MPA Cole-Cole model can be written as:

$$m_{MPA \text{ Cole-Cole}} = \{\rho_0, \varphi_{max}, \tau\varphi, C\}$$

The MPA parametrisation replace the strongly-correlated parameters m_0 and C of the classic Cole-Cole model with the weakly-correlated parameters φ_{max} and C (Fiandaca et al., 2018), to improve the resolution retrieved from inversion IP data of the classical Cole-Cole model.

The results of the inversion process are shown in figures below, with a map of the average chargeability for a depth of 1-10m:

Figure 5. Phase map for the first ten meters depth.

From the map is visible the correlation between the shallower phase and the southern sedimentary domain.

As known, the AIP shows a high correlation with fine grains chargeable materials (silt and clays in conglomerates here) confirming its main spectral sensitivity to small time constants (quick polarization).

Increasing the slice's depth (figure 6) at a depth of 40-50m, localized chargeable anomalies are visible. The large chargeable domain is still localized in the sediment-dominated south-eastern area, as expected, but are interesting the localized anomalies (red box) in the north in the geological volcanic domain. It is possible, for these AIP anomalies, to compare them with ground IP given the good overlapping between lines as visible from figure 3.

Figure 6. Average Phase slice for a depth of 40-50m. The colorscale is the same of figure 4.

A comparison of ground IP with Airborne IP is shown in figure 7, for sections included in the red box of figure 6:

Figure 7. Comparison of Airborne (top) and Ground (bottom) IP modelled phases (in mrad).

As visible from figure 7, the AIP chargeable body shown in the depth slice is confirmed by the ground IP modelled section. As expectable, the resolution and the chargeability value of the ground models are different respect to the ground, but still congruent and laterally coherent with the airborne models. For this section, the ground-data modelled

time constant spans from a range that goes from $1e-03s$ in the shallow subsurface to $3s$ in depth, in correspondence to the chargeable domain (80m in elevation) shown in figure 7.

Another example from the north is shown in figure 8.

Figure 8. Another comparison of Airborne IP modelling (top) and ground IP (bottom) modelled phases (in mrad).

Even for this section, the correlation is robust from AIP to ground, and the modelled time constants span in the same range of the previous one.

As general consideration, for the entire survey area a good correlation between the modelled AIP and the ground is observable.

CONCLUSIONS

With this contribution presented a case study of integration between airborne and ground IP on real data.

Modelling the airborne and the ground data using the same consistent approach appears crucial to recover encouraging comparable models and to make possible the use of the spectral content contained in AEM. This allows to get new insights from the recorded signals and to add extra information to the exploration.

The time constant, as expectable, plays a crucial role in the differences between the airborne and the ground results but, as seen from the examples, the EM data shown sensitivity to the IP effects even for time constant higher than 3. Moreover, inverting the AEM data with the proposed approach, allows to reduce equivalences and to model the maximum phase consistently in depth.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

For this work we acknowledge PanGlobal Inc mining company and his VP Mr. Jim Royall for allowing us to present the data.

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